

SZ-HB-III-01-06 Search for inclusion specialist for professional exchange (English)

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Doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091497
ID	SZ-HB-III-01-06
Title	Search for inclusion specialist for professional exchange
Educational area	#higher-education
Persona	P: Nadine - Student https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091292
Short description	As part of her educational studies, Nadine is looking for a specialist to facilitate professional exchange on the topic of inclusive education.
Result	Using the BuddyFinder, Nadine finds a lecturer, contacts them via chat, and gains access to practical exercises.
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem scenario• Activity scenario• Process "Search for practitioner"
Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Nadine is registered at BIRD• Nadine is logged in to BIRD
Components	#workspace #buddyfinder #chat
Services / tools	

Problem scenario

Introduction

Nadine is in the middle of her studies in education and mathematics and is having difficulties in one of her seminars in inclusive education. To improve in this area and successfully complete the exam, she would like to exchange ideas with a specialist.

Problem definition

Nadine is looking for a specialist who is particularly well-versed in inclusive education and also has expertise in "emotion regulation in people/students/individuals with ADHD." Unfortunately, finding a professional is difficult, and she has no contacts in her personal circle that she could use.

Background and context

Nadine wants to complete learning units on the topic of emotion regulation. When searching for specialists, it is particularly important to her that her data is handled securely during the search and matching process and that it does not later surface in a data breach.

Impact of the problem (on the Persona)

Without professional expertise, Nadine cannot solve her task in the seminar, as it is an explicit requirement in order to prepare for a subsequent internship.

Pre BIRD attempts at a solution

Nadine has already spoken to various people at her University. However, they either didn't have enough time or lacked the practical experience. She also attempted to reach out to people in her personal network, but was unsuccessful.

Activity scenario

Process "Search for specialist"

Step 1: Nadine opens the BuddyFinder and fills out the search query as follows:

- City: Potsdam
- Subject: Educational Science, Pedagogy
- Specialization: Inclusive Education, Emotion Regulation, ADHD
- Looking for: Specialist, at least 3 years of professional experience
- Group or Individual: Individual

Step 2: The Buddy Finder suggests a person (lecturer) at Nadine's university who already offered a tutorial on this topic last semester. This person worked in special education for 5 years before becoming a lecturer. The Buddy Finder also suggests expanding her search to include other universities.

Step 3: Nadine looks at the profile and decides to make contact.

Step 4: Nadine sends a contact request to the lecturer via the Buddy Finder.

Step 5: Nadine receives a notification that her contact request has been accepted.

Step 6: Nadine explains her concerns to the lecturer via the chat function.

Step 7: Nadine then receives an invitation to the lecturer's work area, where she completes.